

Image segmentation in the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. using YOLOv8 algorithm

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Abstract

Coral reefs play a crucial role in the intricate marine ecosystem for its impact in multiple fields. However, corals are currently facing unprecedented threats, particularly in Hong Kong, emphasizing the urgency of coral conservation and studies. The brain coral *Platygyra* sp., one of the most common in Hong Kong can provide valuable insights into the overall health of coral ecosystems. Understanding the need for precise data on the brain coral *Platygyra* sp., a specialized model has been developed for underwater brain coral *Platygyra* sp. image segmentation. This model is trained on a customized dataset and the YOLOv8 network. However, it faces challenges such as indistinctive boundaries and underwater photography limitations that hinder improvements in precision. Despite facing challenges, the model achieved the highest precision rate of 0.936, recall rate of 0.755, and mAP@50 rate of 0.841. The precise identification of the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. aids scientists in restoration and conservation efforts, providing critical information on their health condition and the distribution of the overall ecosystem.

1. Introduction

Coral serves as an important member of the complex marine ecosystem. Corals possess important medical values in cancer and AIDS treatments and other surgeries [1], reflect climate change, and generate over 30 billion dollars in human economic benefits [2].

Despite their importance, coral ecosystems face unprecedented threats. In Hong Kong, the diversity of coral types diminishes by 40% [3]. This notable decline is by Hong Kong's severe pollution triggered by rapid urbanization and industrialization in the 20th century, underlining the urgency of effective coral restorations and protection approaches. The brain coral *Platygyra* sp. one of the most common corals in Hong Kong, can indicate the general coral conditions there and provide insights for biologists and ecologists in addressing the issue of coral decline. Con-

sequently, obtaining precise data on the distribution and conditions of the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. is crucial for the effective conservation and monitoring process. Thus, a specialized model has been developed to detect the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. and separate them out of the background in a large number of underwater imaging photographs. The YOLOv8 model was trained on a custom database comprising 1,090 high-resolution color images that was all labeled by Anylabeling tool.

To achieve higher precision, training software indexes were altered in each trial. However, because of several challenges like the indistinctive boundaries of the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. and limitations of underwater photography hinder the further improvement of precision.

Eventually, the model achieved the highest precision rate of 0.936, the highest recall rate of 0.755, and the highest mAP@50 rate of 0.841. The quick and precise identification of the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. helps scientists with restoration and conservation while reflecting the health condition and distribution of the brain coral *Platygyra* sp.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Dataset

The source for the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. dataset is an MP4 video filmed underwater in Sai Kung Town, Hong Kong in 2023. Figure 1 indicates the location of video filming. The video is utilized for the survey of coral distribution and coral bleaching in Hong Kong. The video was converted into images by frames, and images containing the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. were selected to construct the brain coral database of 1090 images in the format of jpg. In order to save storage space, the images had been resized

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Figure 1: The location marked by the red star represents the place for underwater MP4 video filming.

to 3840×2160 pixels, with color space of RGB16. In total, 901 images are labeled and 188 images are unlabeled. Figure 2 A-D are sample images from the brain coral dataset. The dataset Table 1 is randomly separated into train and val

Table 1: Dataset for network training.

Item	Number	Proportion
training set	740	82%
validation set	161	18%
test set	161	18%
Total	901	100%

Figure 2: Demonstration of images from the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. dataset.

two sections through a Python file named splits.py. Randomizing the sequence helps to reduce the effect of the sequence on the final output, increasing the reliability of the eventual outcome. Train contains 760 images and labels for the training process whilst val contains 161 images and labels for the validation process.

2.2. Annotation

Because the boundaries for corals are relatively irregular and complicated, utilizing the conventional method of an-

notation will consume more time and effort since the whole boundary needs to be marked with points [4]. Thus, an alternative approach is utilized using Anylabelling (version 0.3.3) and an auto-labeling model Segment Anything (Mobile SAM) for image annotation since they require less time devotion [5]. The model Mobile SAM is a small model with a fast inference speed and high accuracy. During the labeling process, we utilize points(+) to select points inside the object. The model will automatically update the boundaries according to the coordinates of the point. Often, the labeling generated by the model is accurate with only 2 or 3 points inside the object selected, unlike the conventional models. The blurred boundaries in some images, since all images are not pre-processed, create hardships for automatic labeling models, generating labels with low accuracy. In those circumstances with imprecise boundaries produced, we have to adjust the object annotation by utilizing Point(-) to eliminate the undesired parts included and use Edit Object to the location of the points on the boundary. Therefore, despite the auto-labeling model Segment Anything (Mobile SAM) can reduce our workload, the model does not make the right

semantics at any time. The labels contain only one class, with the class name "platygyra". Figure 3 are examples of annotations.

During the labeling process, a JSON file that matches the image will be generated. The JSON file stores the version of Anylabelling, label names, and the x-y coordinate of the points on the boundary. To match the requirements of standard training data structure of YOLOv8, the JSON files were transformed into txt files by a Python program 'labelme2yolo.py'.

2.3. CNN module YOLOv8

The YOLO (You Only Look Once) networks have developed over time through various editions and enhancements. Launched first in 2015, YOLOv1 gained rapid popularity owing to its exceptional speed and accuracy. After YOLOv1, Ultralytics [6] subsequently released YOLOv2 through YOLOv7 in the past 8 years, with each version demonstrating improved performance Figure 4. YOLOv8 is the latest version released, representing the cutting-edge model for both image segmentation and object segmentation [7].

The YOLOv8 model conducts multiple tasks like segmentation, segmentation, pose estimation, tracking, and classification [8]. The YOLOv8 network also provides a semantic segmentation model called the YOLOv8-Seg model. CSPDarknet53 feature extractor, followed by a C2f module instead of the traditional YOLO neck architecture is the backbone of the network [9]. The C2f module is followed by two segmentation heads, which learn to predict the semantic segmentation masks for the input image. The model has similar segmentation heads to YOLOv8, consisting of five segmentation modules and a prediction layer. The YOLOv8-Seg model has achieved great results on various object segmentation and semantic segmentation benchmarks while maintaining high speed and efficiency [9].

The reason for selecting YOLOv8 as the network is first because of its fast speed. Unlike YOLOv5, it changed the backbone to C2f, which decreased the size of the model and efficiently increased the speed. Figure 5 clearly shows the increase in speed of the YOLOv8 model. Moreover, YOLOv8 has a significant increase in accuracy (mAP 50-95). In previous research comparing YOLOv5 and YOLOv8's performance, YOLOv8s has a 3.22% higher mAP than YOLOv8 [10].

3. Experiment

3.1. Experimental environment

The training and prediction were running on Nvidia RTX A6000, with a GPU memory of 48GB GDDR6 and error-correcting code (ECC), 300 W max power consumption [11]. The experimental software environment is PyTorch 1.12.1 deep learning framework, YOLOv8 0.145 training

model, and Python version 3.7.13.

3.2. Metrics evaluating performance

mAP@50 (Mean of Average Precision when IOU threshold equals 0.5) is a metric that evaluates the holistic performance of the model by calculating the average of AP (Average Precision).

$$mAP = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n AP_i \quad (1)$$

P(Precision) and R(Recall) rates indicate the percentage of objects being correctly classified. (1-Precision rate) represents the percentage of other categories classified as the target category. (1-Recall rate) represents the percentage of target objects classified as other categories

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

F1-score represents the harmonic mean of the precision rate and the recall rate and reflects the overall accuracy of the model. A high F1 score represents a high precision rate and also a high recall rate, while a high average of the recall rate and the precision rate might represent a high value of one rate but a low value of another.

$$F1\ Score = \frac{2 * Recall * Precision}{Recall + Precision} \quad (4)$$

Using bounding boxes for the calculation of IOU isn't accurate as an index since different shapes of coral can possess the same bounding box. This indicates that despite the high IOU, poor accuracy of segmentation can occur [12]. Therefore, this metric is excluded from evaluating the performance of the model.

3.3. Experiment procedure

The coral segmentation model went through multiple training trials to enhance its performance. Figure 7 provides a collection of specific training environments and results for each trial. Initially, the dataset was trained for 100 epochs with a default batch size of 16, utilizing the 'YOLOv8n-seg.pt' model, consisting of 400 training images, 100 validation images, and a default learning rate of 0.01. However, the results were unsatisfactory, with a low mAP@50 of 0.73, indicating a precision issue as 27% of objects were misclassified.

In response, the number of epochs was increased to 300, but the model stopped training at the 173 epoch as no significant improvement was observed in the last 50 epochs. The mAP@50 improved to 0.759, prompting adjustments to the training approach. The number of training images was then

Figure 3: A-C: Samples of labeled photos inside the dataset.

Figure 4: Graphic illustration of the development of the YOLO network [9].

Figure 5: Graphic illustration of the development of the YOLO network [9].

increased to 500, the batch size was raised to 32, and the epochs trained reached 139 before the training process was automatically halted by patience. Despite these changes, the overall performance showed only minor improvements, with a reduced mAP@50 of 0.7 and an increased recall rate of 0.745.

Further modifications were made by increasing the batch size to 64 and reducing the learning rate to 0.001, aiming for higher precision requirements in the learning process. The model was trained for 194 epochs, automatically stopped

by a patience of 50, resulting in an improved mAP@50 of 0.78 and a consistent recall rate of 0.745. To enhance mAP@50 further, adjustments were made to the dataset, with 450 training photos and 150 validation photos introduced to allow the model more time to adjust its weights. Despite an initial decrease in mAP@0.5 to 0.6, precision increased to 0.874, and the recall rate decreased to 0.66.

To increase mAP@50, the training model was switched to YOLOv8l-seg.pt with a default batch size of 16. Despite the larger model containing approximately 43.7 million parameters (20 times more than YOLOv8n), the impact on precision and mAP@50 was insignificant Figure 5. Due to a decline in precision after the reallocation of images, random allocation into training or validation sets were implemented, along with an increased batch size of 32, resulting in improved mAP@50 and recall rate.

Subsequent attempts to enhance performance included increasing the number of epochs trained to 600, but it automatically stopped at the 294th epoch. Another attempt at 1000 epochs with a decreased learning rate of 0.001 yielded 291 epochs due to patience, resulting in an increased mAP@50 of 0.663. To mitigate the impact of pa-

Figure 6: Graphic illustration of the development of the YOLO network [9].

tience, the patience parameter was set to 50000, ensuring it would not be reached within the 1000 epochs training limit. Then mAP@50 increases to 0.75, indicating improvements in results. Finally, we decided to increase the number of photos and labels inside the dataset. This change is relatively successful as our mAP@50 increased to 0.841, demonstrating a significant improvement.

4. Result

The highest result for precision rate, recall rate, and mAP@50 rate are 0.936, 0.755, and 0.841 each. From the experiment procedures and the result, we compared and contrasted 2 different trials, number 10 and number 11 which are only different in the numbers of photos in valediction and train. Figure 8a and Figure 8b are two F1-scores over the confidence curve. The F1-score curve of the 11th trial is higher and flatter than the graph of the 10th graph, demonstrating a higher recall rate and precision rate of the model. This suggests that the increase in dataset picture numbers will have a significant impact on the overall accuracy. This also suggests further research directions to improve the accuracy as the model had better performance with more photos inside the dataset.

The performance of two different models of YOLOv8 is also compared, trials three and seven [Figure 8.] as the newly labeled dataset and the few changes between train and valediction sets have little impact on the overall performance. Figure 8c and Figure 8d are the f1-score curves for each trial. This reveals that the 7th trial and the 3rd trial will have similar average performance as one has a flat graph but low values and the other has a greater distinction in values, despite it having a higher greatest f1 score. Figure 9 is the

comparison of the performance of each model on the photos outside of the domain of the valediction and training sets. The performance of the 3rd model and the 7th model are largely similar, indicating the minor impact of changing to a model with more parameters.

5. Challenges

Overall, the mAP@50 altered from 0.6-0.85, and further changes in the training environment made minor changes to the overall performance. This is because the various challenges of image quality underwater hindered performance improvement. Challenges faced inside the research are firstly the indistinctive boundaries of the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. which doesn't possess bright colors. Instead, the brain coral *Platygyra* sp. possesses colors similar to the seafloor like brown or ivory, making it unclear compared to other colorful marine organisms. Moreover, the images are taken underwater, which includes challenges like haze-like effects, color cast, and lighting interference. Those problems are caused by the underwater environment lowering the quality of the images, creating challenges for coral segmentation. Moreover, the corals often contain irregular and complex boundaries, such as in Figure 10. Also, corals may possess indistinctive boundaries as the dead corals and living corals are mixed up as indicated in Figure 11, increasing the difficulties for precise segmentation. Those challenges prevent the precision rate, the recall rate, and mAP@50 to increase to higher levels such as 90% or even 95%.

6. Conclusion

Overall, our model trained with the YOLOv8-seg network performed at the highest precision of 0.936, recall rate

time	batch_size	learning_rate	epochs	dataset	train_number	val_number	train_model	mAP@50	P	R	Patience
1	16	0.01	100	old	400	100	yolov8n-seg	0.73	0.838	0.713	50
2	16	0.01	173	old	400	100	yolov8n-seg	0.759	0.936	0.721	50
3	32	0.01	139	old	500	100	yolov8n-seg	0.7	0.858	0.745	50
4	64	0.001	194	old	500	100	yolov8n-seg	0.78	0.868	0.755	50
5	64	0.01	300	old	450	150	yolov8l-seg	0.6	0.874	0.66	50
6	16	0.01	300	new	450	150	yolov8l-seg	0.656	0.872	0.628	50
7	32	0.01	300	new	491	109	yolov8l-seg	0.693	0.871	0.636	50
8	32	0.01	294	new	491	109	yolov8l-seg	0.633	0.827	0.62	50
9	32	0.001	291	new	491	109	yolov8l-seg	0.663	0.827	0.623	50
10	32	0.01	1000	new	491	109	yolov8l-seg	0.75	0.842	0.654	50000
11	32	0.01	1000	new	760	161	yolov8l-seg	0.841	0.889	0.75	50000

Figure 7: Training results of each trail

Figure 8: F1-score over the confidence curve on Figure 7

of 0.755, and mAP@50 rate of 0.841. Through the training process, we detected several challenges throughout the training process and concluded that on our image segmentation task, the YOLOv8n model, with its current level of parameters, is good enough for training and inference

7. Limitations and Future Works

Firstly, the segmentation model focuses only on the brain coral *Platygyra* sp., indicating a low applicability of the model in other fields. It is crucial to increase the type of

marine organisms included in the dataset in further research. Moreover, the images are not pre-processed, reflecting low resolutions, blurred boundaries, and color variation problems that could be potentially solved with image processing. To optimize the performance of the segmentation model, it is necessary that our future works involve pre-processing the images.

Figure 9: In comparison of the performance of the 3rd trial and 7th trial, the result of the third model is on the left and the result of the 7th model is on the right.

Figure 10: Image sample illustrating the instances of irregular and complex borders, imposing challenges for the labeling.

Figure 11: Image sample illustrating the instances of mixed dead and living coral, increasing the difficulty of labeling.

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